

Either KNO_3 or NH_4NO_3 solutions (20 c.c.) were pipetted into a flask, different volumes of $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution were added and the mixture was made up to 60 c.c. with distilled water.

The interfacial tensions were measured by the method described earlier. The results obtained at 30° are shown graphically in Fig. 1.

DISCUSSION

The figure shows peaks corresponding to the formation of the following complexes :

- (a) $\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$; $2\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$; $4\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$
 (b) $\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$; $2\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$; $4\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.

FIG. 1

$M/10\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ added in c.c. to $M\text{-10-alkalinitrate}$ (20 c.c.).

These results confirm the findings of Nayar and others (*loc. cit.*). Further, *sec*-octyl alcohol behaves as sensitively as *n*-butyl acetate in the indication of complex formation in solution.

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INTERFACIAL TENSION OF LIQUIDS HAVING H-BOND RING
STRUCTURE AND COMPLEX FORMATION. PART III. THE
SYSTEM $\text{NaNO}_3\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$

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Measurements of interfacial tension between *n*-butyl acetate against a series of mixed solutions of NaNO_3 and $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ indicate the formation of the complexes: (1) $4\text{NaNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (2) $2\text{NaNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and (3) $\text{NaNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in solution.

It was observed by Le Blanc and Noyes (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1890, 6, 386) that solubility of $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in water at ordinary temperature was increased by the presence of KNO_3 , but decreased by NaNO_3 . The same conclusion was arrived at by Kanitz, Glasstone and others (*ibid.*, 1897, 22, 347; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2134). The difference in the behaviour of the potassium salt from that of sodium salt was ascribed to the formation of its potassium double salt with lead nitrate in solution. Lewis and others (Dissert. Breslau, 1908; *J. Chem. Soc.* 1923, 123, 2134; *Trans. Faraday Soc.* 1907, 2, 199; *Z. elektrochem.*, 1904, 10, 77; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1898, 17, 327) however, observed that the addition of either KNO_3 or NaNO_3 to a solution of $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ caused a considerable decrease in plumbous ion concentration, thus indicating complex formation in each case, though to a greater extent with potassium salt. The conductance, viscosity and thermometric measurements (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 27A 293; *this Journal*, 1951, 28, 112) led Nayar and Pande to conclude that no complex formation took place between NaNO_3 and $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, but transport number measurements (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 27A, 359) indicated a tendency for the formation of complex, as originally pointed out by Lewis. They, however, observed that definite complexes obeying stoichiometric laws did not seem to exist in NaNO_3 — $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ — H_2O system.

The authors have examined the possibility of complex formation by the method of interfacial tension measurement.

EXPERIMENTAL

Lead nitrate and sodium nitrate (E. Merck) were recrystallised from distilled water and their stock solutions ($M/10$) were prepared in distilled water.

FIG. 1

NaNO_3 solution (20 c.c.) was pipetted into a flask to which different volumes of $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution were added and the total volume was made up to 60 c.c. with distilled water. In another set of experiments 10 c.c. of $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution were taken and different volumes of NaNO_3 solution were added and the mixture was made up to 60 c.c.

The interfacial tensions were measured in the same manner as described in Part I (this issue, p. 287) at 30° . The results obtained are shown graphically in Fig. 1.

D I S C U S S I O N

Fig 1 shows peaks corresponding to the formation of the following complexes; NaNO_3 , $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$; 2NaNO_3 , $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_3$; 4NaNO_3 , $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_4$. These results are in conformity with the conclusions (qualitative) arrived at by Lewis and others (*loc. cit.*). This method of interfacial tension measurements of a liquid with unstable H-bond ring structure being extremely sensitive, opens a wide field in the investigations of the existence of complex in salt solutions, in as much as it reveals that definite complexes, obeying stoichiometric laws, also seem to exist in NaNO_3 — $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ — H_2O system, just as in the case of analogous potassium and ammonium nitrate systems. The authors consider that the following equilibrium sequence exists:

as a result of changes in the interionic character, due to variations in electrolyte concentration, where M is either potassium, ammonium or sodium in the system.

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